

To analyze Transformational Leadership and OCB an effect on ...

To analyze Transformational Leadership and OCB an effect on Organizational Commitment: Higher Education Teaching Faculty of Pakistan

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Abstract

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is denoted to additional efforts or out of context role played by employee(s) which is beyond one's formal job description prescribed by the organization. OCB is not actually a written agreement or it may not be required from an ordinary worker, but this behavior has great importance and likely desired in the organizational settings. Leader toils to his level best to mold follower's (employee) attitude towards organizational targets. Leadership remained a vital topic under various theorists but the Transformational Leadership was the most prominent. As higher education institutes are a hub of high level education providing places of any country, subsequently the educational standard and quality of deliverance have much more importance for them. The behavioral difference amongst university teachers' worth require professional growth so teacher ship cannot be isolated from the development. Quality enhancement is essential for the individuals who are related with teaching and learning environment. Here, to explore the effects of OCB on the OC explicitly in connection to higher education teaching faculty of Pakistan. It portrays the significance of OCB in the enhancement of efficiency of firm and furthermore to determine the influencing and generating factors of OC. This study comprehends the correlation of transformational leadership, T & D chances, work and life plans & empowerment activities with organizational commitment and to evaluate significance of OCB of teachers in the triumph of their respective institutions in Pakistan.

Keywords: Organizational Citizenship Behavior, organizational commitment, Training & Development, Transformational Leadership.

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Introduction

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is very frequently used in numerous studies in recent past, and it has proved its effectiveness in organizational settings over all. It is a kind of selfless and reward less (either in materialistic form or in the form of appreciation) hard work put forward by employee(s) for a non-formal activities without a greed of recognition from the high ups. Such type of behaviors are pigeonholed as a discrete quality of the worker which enlightened the reason why few workers show considerably a selflessly attitude as compare to others. (Koster & Sanders, 2006, Turnipseed & Murkison, 1996). Organizational citizenship behaviors are activities which has not labelled or not even claimed through prescribed occupational duties (Farh, Zhong & Organ, 2004). On the other side, Burns (1978) is of the view that leadership has minimum preeminence it's a source of communication between them (Boss and employee, Lo, Ramayah, Min, & Songan, 2010). Leadership remained a vital topic under various theorists but initial concept of Transformational Leadership was initiated by the most prominent theorists J.M. Burns (1978). (Bushra, Usman, & Naveed, 2011).

The big data, or other search engines has created excess to the flood of information and awareness, and started a fierce battle of completion amongst the organizations in the contemporary time and space. To gain maximum advantage in this competitive scenario, all the organizations are struggling very hard to win complete commitment from their employee(s) so that they can move with time (Lok and Crawford, 2001). Wilson and western (2000) viewed that an employee can become an asset and supportive for the firm if he has given proper training and development plans as well as directional clear sense. By making the teachers empower in the decision taking procedure produce positive outcomes. The perception of ownership develops through letting the teachers to take part in decision taking procedure through empowered work environment and then those teachers would become reasonably fruitful professionals and leaders. It is observed that the teachers show much more commitment and dedication when they find that their efforts are result oriented (Dee, Henkin & Duemer, 2002). An organizational settings where polices of work-life are made available, an environment of learning takes place then those organizations transform into zealous learning organizations (Yong, 2000). A developing country cannot develop without a good educational system and the teachers are the drivers of that system. Effective, capable and quality teachers can bring success in any education system (Joolideh & Yeshodhara, 2008). The manner through which services are delivered by workers governs the extraordinary worth of performances (Bienstock, DeMoranville & Smith 2003). It is viewed that Pakistan is a below investigated state, hence to explore the depth of organizational citizenship behavior in university educators of Pakistan (Aycan et al., 2000). As higher education institutes are a hub of high level education providing places of any country, subsequently the educational standard and quality of deliverance have much more importance for them. Under consideration reasons behind the behavioral difference amongst university teachers such as some teacher demonstrate comparatively more cooperation and helpful attitude in comparison to others. Worth requires professional growth so teacher ship cannot be isolated from the development.

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Transformational Leadership

Leadership theory of transformational leader persuades his/her followers (employees) to bring positive results to the team. Moreover, leadership focuses on what which had not done before. It comprises with well trained and enigmatic leadership abilities. This theory insists on participatory leadership process. The results create an ability to change leaders or any employee of the organizations through motivation and performance levels (AlQudah, 2011). In prior studies, it has been found that transformational theory of leadership is more valuable for the organization as together leader & follower work for the betterment of it driven by trust and respect as well as shared visions and values (Avolio & Bass, 1994). It has been observed that organizational commitment and leadership theory has a positive correlation. (Avolio et al. 2004). There are various aspects of this theory but the four most important are i.e. logical motivation, stimulating inspiration, ideal effect, and distinct deliberation. All these points have observed available in connection to OC in different studies, for instance, we can notice the connection of transformational leadership and OC and its various aspects. They all in origin considered to be connected. (Tseng and Kang 2008). So, this under consideration study also desires to determine the effect that transformational leadership theory has got their workers' commitment towards the organization.

Training and Development Chances

Training and development (T&D) has gone through drastic variations during previous one decade (Garavan, Barnicle & Heraty, 1993). T&D is methodical pattern which has numerous applications of procedures, actions and skills. Scholars has taken training as value added in the profession. Garavan (1997) mentions that however, development is a progression in bit by bit. This is the fact of contemporary time to provide skills and proper education to human resources if you want to get better results from the employees. Because it is now globally accepted truth that if the employees are well trained then you can excel into this competitive world of business (Khayyat, 1998). Training brings remarkably constructive impact on the management and the workforce (Kallenberg and Moody, 1994). According to the views of Antonacopoulou, (2000) that different organizations finance trainings to reach to their objectives. Further, Liu (2006) explains that training provides satisfaction which creates in fact the back ground of the organizational commitment amongst the employees. If organizations give clear sense of direction to their employees along with training and development plans then this work force would become very much supportive for the firm to achieve their objectives (Wilson &Western, 2000). Another big challenge for the organizations is to retain their professional employees. It is observed that training is one of the vital tactic to retain professionals in the organization (Stassen & Templer, 2004). Training is a tool which can rise training usefulness when practical work is a focal point at that stage need analysis is significant (Baalen & Hoogendoorn 1999). Brown, Boyle & Boyle (2001) viewed that process of perpetual learning of teachers is mostly ignored whereas continuous learning and professional improvement are fundamental to teacher professionalism. Quest for attaining the competitive advantage it is essential to obtain new skills and knowledge. The basic obstacle in executing the value managing is lack of perpetual availability trainings (Masters, 1996). The core motive behind training and development is to enrich the employees with skills, professional attitudes and knowledge which is indispensable for

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effective task performance (Berge, Verneil, Berge, Davis & Smith, 2002). Earlier scholars observed that it is a training which puts psychological effect over the employees, when they have given trainings the employees sense that firm have worried about their employees then their commitment upsurges (Chang, 1999).

Work Life Plans

Scholars commonly connect the job features, the family responsibilities, workplace organization & parenting attitudes, and job conflicts (Glass & Riley, 1998). Scholarship reveals that extended labor, consecutive overtime, afternoon shifts, strict working hours, mentally and physically challenging works and failure to leave for emergencies are the factors which become vital in producing work household clashes (Pleck, Staines & Lang, 1980). Work life plan can be defined as flexible working timings, pauses from work, training opportunities, and arrangements for improved working environment (Maxwell, 2005). During last one decade interest of the organizations as well as the employees have increased very fast concerned with work family programs (Schwartz, 1996). Employee's decision making related with the firm are affected by the balance between the work & life on account of that if the clash occurs between work & life balance at that moment frustration develops which causes negative effect on family life & worker performance. A lot of firms trying to implement various strategies to overcome such genuine issues of employees but still a long way ahead to tackle it completely with comprehensive and extensive steps are required to safeguard a better balance (Deery, 2008). Work place flexibility is key issue now a days, because employee is much more concern about time as compared to money as he/she has to fulfill the work, community and family needs altogether (Hall, 2001).

Different scholars verified the impact of work plan & family life outcomes that comprises changeable schedules, child care awareness as well as childcare support, parental holidays on organizational commitment. Hence it was established that when the worker has access to family life and work plans displayed remarkably better organizational commitment and indicated less intent to quit the employments (Grover and Crooker 1995). Work plan and family life are considerably positive associated to organizational commitment (Dockel et al., 2006).

Application of Empowerment

More than fifty years empowerment or sharing remained a vital question of investigation and research (Nykodym, Simonetti, Nielsen & Welling, 1994). In fact empowerment can be defined in a very simple words that it is an ability of a worker to make decisions which he/she feels suitable to that situation may be contrary to the employer. One component of this type of ability of a worker is that he has liberty to make decisions and after taking decisions the worker, further, would be able to perpetuate taking decisions (Guy, 2003). Various scholars deliberated over the empowerment; the actual meaning of empowerment is handing over power or authorizing someone (Tulloch, 1993). Empowerment is considered that it is a portion of development, which combines psychology of subordination that is very much affected by supervisory attitude through empowering the subordinate (Pastor, 1996). If the organization requires quality of services then the best way is to empower the employee which will bring considerable outcomes (Samat, Ramayah & Saad, 2006). Tertiary firms are

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comparatively quite extra sensitive to their quality of services, therefore gaining more positive results the firms gradually empower their employees (Cacioppe, 1998). Procedural act of empowerment is fundamentally inspire the employees to utilize their experience and skill so that they perform efficiently (Eccles, 1993). Workers empowerment comprises dedication and participation (Val & Lloyd, 2002). Researchers viewed that it (empowerment) has positive connection to job fulfillment. Lack of empowerment considerably puts effect on the work to quit firm (Avey, Hughes, Norman, Luthans, 2007). The empowerment can distinguish it into two elements i.e. behavior element and psychology element (Meyerson & Kline, 2007). Worker's faith increases on the manager as much he/she is empowered (Moye & Henkin, 2006). When employee is empowered in the process of decision making which leads to greater extent of accountability to both ends on attaining job and client satisfaction (Jarrar & Zairi, 2002). Teachers' empowerment is also very crucial means by empowering teachers organization help them to enhance their leadership abilities, develops work and life quality and progress in their professionalism (Dee, Henkin & Duemer, 2003).

The organizational triumph is dependent on the workers commitment with the organization which can be acquired through engaging the worker (Denton, 1994). Organizational development depends on the adaptation of innovation and modern ideas so the employees should be equipped with modern knowledge and skills (McEwan & Sackett, 1997). The level of asking about empowerment differs considerably (Greasley, Bryman, Naismith & Soetano, 2008). Empowerment enhances the level of organizational learning which eventually increases the level of organizational commitment (Bhatnagar, 2007).

Organizational Commitment

The organizational commitment getting more and more importance in the organizational settings now a days. This concept has taken roots during last 30 years (Putterill & Rohrer, 1995). There are various factors which can develop organizational commitment amongst the employees, one of them is if the organization provides opportunities to their employees to perform challenging tasks (Chew & Chan, 2007). Employee performance can be enhanced and level of organizational commitment can be increased by providing changes at workplace and employees empowerment. (Parish, Cadwallader & Busch 2008). There are various benefits of organizational commitment i.e. it curtails the major issues of an organization such as absenteeism percentage and turnover rate (Jernigan, Beggs & Kohut, 2002). Boon and Arumugan (2006) viewed that practices of the management of an organization and organizational culture may be synthesized to achieve more organizational commitment, as well it is also observed that employees relationship pay back in the form of organizational commitment (McCabe & Garavan, 2008). The most challenging task for an organization is the approximation of the level of commitment amongst their workers and find out means to uplift the commitment level (Liu, 2006). Organizational commitment requires from an individual to show loyalty with the organization, remain stick with the organization and attach his own interests with the interest of the organization (Brewer, 1996). An employee with the zeal of his commitment contributes remarkably to the performance of the organization (Freund & Carmeli, 2003). The task of employee retention can be achieved through OC (Stallworth, 2004). The organizational commitment can produce more and more extra role behaviors (Foote, Seipel, Johnson & Duffy, 2005). It has proved through past studies that OC is a

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foretelling of OCB on account of its considerable impact on organizational citizenship behavior (Liu, 2008).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Different scholars commented on climate of an organization, they viewed that organizational climate is expressively connected with the organizational citizenship behavior. Climate of an organization develops perception amongst the employees and manipulate their inclination towards hard work, it increases involvement with work and they eagerly become a part of an OCB (Dimitriades, 2007). A prime responsibility of a manager to give extra care for the enhancement of OCB amongst their employees. Because customer perception regarding quality of service and efficiency of the organization are directly linked to OCB (Torlak & Koc, 2007). OCB of a teacher may not vary as they are associated with field of education or because of seniority or gender difference. Teachers are perceived positively regarding organizational citizenship behavior (Yılmaz & dan, 2008). OCB is considered as an extra burden of the organization put on by an employee enthusiastically (Schepman, & Zarate, 2008). Teachers extra performance at work place are observed when those teachers possess concerned working capability (Kagaari & Munene, 2007). Organizational citizenship behavior has got very much importance during ten to fifteen years (Cohen & Kol, 2004). Organizational citizenship behaviors are produced lower when in the organization attitudes of the employees are not favorable (Lara & Rodríguez, 2006). Teacher containments are affected through without work attitudes. Such attitudes improve the instruction worth as well as become a source of advantage to institute (Lara, 2008). An organization has to develop mutual human resource plans and organizational commitment within their employees if they want to strengthen learning behavior (Yong, 2000).

As it was earlier discussed that Organizational Citizenship Behavior in fact determines the workers' willing attitude to put in efforts and conjoin with organization to play their role for enhancement of the productivity of the organization, customer satisfaction and worker contentment. Better organizational citizenship behavior signifies workers' keen interest and approach to accept changes which were adopted by management through implementing innovative methodologies (Jung & Hong, 2008). Now a days organizations have assumed that for gaining competitive advantage they have to improve workers in put efforts and for the fruitful outcome through workers, their efforts are required which can be beyond their job description (Garg & Rastogi, 2006).

Conclusion

It was considered the effect of above discussed factors which are transformational leadership, T&D chances, and application of empowerment, work & life plans on the OC in Pakistan university teachers. We come to know that betterment of one factor effects over the organizational development and then organizational commitment bring visible change in OCB. Now a days it is quite hard to find labor filled with zeal of commitment with the organization which can cause OCB, particularly in field of teaching because teacher's performance affect the standard of education and as we have already learnt that organizational citizenship behavior can only be possible if teacher show their complete commitment with the organization/university. Above factors analysis made it clear that the

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determinants enhancing organizational commitment are transformational leadership, training & development opportunities, application of empowerment and work life plans, in sum up these all together improve the OCB of Pakistan university faculty. Initiation to evaluate the part of OCB in up lift of educational standard i universities of Pakistan.

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